

Analytical Determination of Iron Oxide in Glasses

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A method is described for estimating iron, present in colloidal dispersion throughout the entire mass of the glass and not in combination with any of the constituent nor linked to the glass structure. The process involves in bringing the dispersed pigment in solution after fusion with potassium pyrosulphate or bisulphate and estimating iron colorimetrically.

The properties of glass, notably those of absorption and emission of infrared, transmission of ultraviolet rays, heat conductance in the molten condition, tendency towards discoloration during annealing, response to decoration, formation of iron colours, working range for shaping, etc., are all associated with the state of oxidation of iron and the way in which oxides are housed in the glass structure¹. Obviously, for a better understanding of the role of iron on these properties, we need know the concentration of the various forms of iron in glass. From a spectrophotometric study of the colours exhibited by iron in alkali-lime-silica and alkali-lime-borosilicate glasses, Moore and Prasad² have established the existence of four different forms of iron, viz., FeO, Fe₂O₃ (coloured), Fe₃O₄ (colorless), and Fe₂O₃, and have also estimated the percentage of each by colour analysis.

Chemical analysis helps estimate only the percentage of the total ferrous and/or ferric iron in glass. The evolution of this colour analysis method has therefore been an outstanding contribution. It was considered worthwhile to study the feasibility of evolving suitable chemical methods for estimating the percentage of all the four forms of iron. The present communication describes how it is possible to estimate the percentage of the iron, which is present in colloidal dispersion throughout the entire mass of glass and is not combined with any of the constituent, nor is linked to its structure. The process consists in bringing this dispersed pigment into solution after fusing the glass sample with potassium pyrosulphate or bisulphate and estimating the iron colorimetrically. The oxide present as network-former or in the interstitial holes as network-modifier does not appear to be disturbed. This shows that the main glass structure is not affected by pyrosulphate or bisulphate fusion, although the possibility of ion exchange taking place between glass and fused salts cannot be ruled out. For a complete picture, the residue from the pyrosulphate fusion was subjected to H⁺ treatment and the total percentage of the residual iron was determined in the usual way. As anticipated, the total % of dispersed iron and that of the residue are very nearly identical with the percentage of the total iron determined directly by the existing method. Attempts are being made to evolve a suitable method for bringing into solution the iron oxide present in the interstitial holes only.

1. Weyl, "Coloured Glass," 1951, p. 89.

2. *J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1949, 33, 336.

EXPERIMENTAL

Procedure

Glass sample (1 g.), ground as finely as for the determination of the alkalis by the Lawrence Smith method, was mixed intimately with six times its weight of powdered potassium pyrosulphate (reagent quality) in an agate mortar, placed on a glazed paper. The mixture was transferred to a silica crucible containing powdered pyrosulphate as the bottom layer ($\approx$ 0.5g.). The mortar and the pestle were dry-washed 3 or 4 times with further quantities of the pyrosulphate powder and transferred to the crucible. Particles scattered during the operation were transferred to the crucible with usual precautions. At the initial stage, the heating was required to be done very slowly in order to avoid any loss due to spattering. The temperature was gradually raised to avoid frothing. The mass was kept in a fused condition to expel most of the sulphurous fumes. Formation of normal potassium sulphate did not present any difficulty during cooling as no platinum crucible was used. At the end, the lid was removed and the crucible was given a rotary motion to obtain a layer of solidified mass on the inner surface of the crucible. Such a layer was easily removed from the crucible. On cooling, the fused mass was dissolved in water (100 ml) containing about 10ml of iron-free H_2SO_4 (conc.). After complete dissolution, the iron was oxidised to ferric state by boiling with HNO_3 , free from iron and oxides of nitrogen. The solution was filtered and the residue, consisting of glass powder without the dispersed iron, was washed free of acids. On cooling, the solution was required to be diluted to 250 or 500 ml, the extent of dilution depending on the iron content of the original glass sample.

Colorimetric process is more suitable for the determination of iron up to 5% in silicates³ and, as such, the procedure outlined by Mellor and Thompson⁴ had been followed. The standard stock solution of iron contained 0.6040g. of pure ammonium ferric alum and 5 ml of iron-free H_2SO_4 per litre (1ml of this solution represented 0.0001g. of Fe_2O_3). The red colour produced by potassium thiocyanate solution with the unknown sample was matched against the colour produced by the standard solution in Nessler's tubes. Naturally, the results will appear to have been affected to the extent it is usual with colorimetric process.

The residue left after filtration was dried and a weighed quantity of the solid was treated separately for the determination of residual iron, after HF treatment in the usual way.

The samples treated by the present method embrace one alkali-lime-silica glass, prepared in the laboratory, the batch composition of which is: SiO_2 , 73.50%; Na_2O , 17.20%; CaO , 7.00%; Fe_2O_3 , 1.25%; Al_2O_3 , 0.60%.

TABLE I
% Iron estimated as Fe_2O_3 and present as:

Type of glass.	Colloidal suspension. (I)	Modifier and network-former. (II)	Total of I & II.	Total % of Fe_2O_3 determined directly.
Container glass	0.0428	0.0765	0.1193	0.1181
Dark green bottle glass	0.1314	0.1641	1.3085	1.3140
Prepared glass	0.0286	1.2150	1.2435	1.2498*

N.B. Duration of heating was 2 hrs.

*Mean of several determinations.

3. Herapath, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1852, 5, 27.

4. "Treatise on Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1938, 2nd ed., p. 186.

It is apparent from Table I that the total iron content of each glass (determined directly as Fe_2O_3) is, according to presumption, in close agreement with the value appearing under column four. The ratio of glass powder to pyrosulphate used was 1:6. With a view to testing if the effect of fusion was independent of the increased fineness of the glass powder, duration of heating, and the quantity of the pyrosulphate used, the bottle glass was powdered to 350 mesh and the process of fusion was repeated using a ratio of 1:10 and under conditions as specified above. The heating was, however, prolonged by half-an-hour more. The washed residue from such fusion process was dried, weighed, and re-fused with a fresh quantity of pyrosulphate with a view to be sure of the absence of any residual colloiddally dispersed ferric iron. The solution obtained after this latter treatment did not give any colour with thiocyanate solution. Table II embraces the results thus obtained.

TABLE II

Colloiddally dispersed iron in dark green bottle glass (No. 2, Table I).

Fineness of glass powder.	Duration of heating in the fused condition.	% Fe_2O_3 in the	
		First melt.	Second melt.
350 mesh	2½ hrs	*0.1316	No colour with the cyanate solution

*0.1314 % according to Table I.

Table II shows that if the glass grains are of impalpable nature, the entire quantity of colloiddally dispersed iron is brought into solution and that a single fusion is quite sufficient to extract the dispersed iron. Further work in this direction is in progress.